

Child Abuse & Neglect

A.Nancy

*Mangayarkarasi College of Women's Education
Paravai, Madurai*

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Abstract

Child abuse and neglect, is the extent to which society is not well known; most of the times that are hidden, many more victims do not mention in a public health problem. Abused and neglected child reaches very few therapeutic institutions. Generally, the cases remain hidden in the family. If the situation was brought in the emergency department is often heavy, life-threatening complications.

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines child maltreatment as “all forms of physical and emotional ill-treatment, sexual abuse, neglect, and exploitation that results in actual or potential harm to the child’s health, development or dignity.” There are four main types of abuse: neglect, physical abuse, psychological abuse and sexual abuse. Abuse is defined as an act of commission and neglect is defined as an act of omission in the care leading to potential or actual harm. Neglect may include inadequate health care, education, supervision, protection from hazards in the environment, and unmet basic needs such as clothing and food. Neglect is the most common form of child abuse. Physical abuse may include beating, shaking, burning, and biting. The threshold for defining corporal punishment as abuse is unclear. Psychological abuse includes verbal abuse, humiliation, and acts that scare or terrorize a child, which may result in future psychological illness of the child. Sexual abuse is defined as “the involvement of dependent, developmentally immature children and adolescents in sexual activities which they do not fully comprehend, to which they are unable to give consent, or that violate the social taboos of family roles.” Some cases of sexual abuse do not need to involve oral, anal, or vaginal penetration and may include exposure to sexually explicit materials, oral-genital contact, genital-to-genital contact, genital-to-anal contact, and genital fondling.

Many approaches were identified in the broad health literature; however, there has been limited application of these approaches to child maltreatment. The most common use was recruiting participants or engaging existing participants using online methods. From the broad health literature, social media and internet-based approaches to surveillance and epidemiologic research appear promising. Many of the approaches are relatively low cost and easy to implement without extensive infrastructure, but there are also a range of limitations for each method. Several methods have a mixed record of validation and sources of error in estimation are not yet understood or predictable. In addition to the problems relevant to other health outcomes, child maltreatment researchers face additional challenges, including the complex ethical issues associated with both internet-based and child maltreatment research. If these issues are adequately addressed, social media and internet-based technologies may be a promising approach to reducing some of the limitations in existing child maltreatment data.

Keywords: Child abuse, child maltreatment, child protective services, news media, neglect, child sexual abuse, Saint-Jacques, M.- C., Villeneuve, P., Turcotte, D., Drapeau, S., Ivers, H. (2011). The role of media in reporting child abuse. *Journal of social service research*, 1-13.

Introduction

Collecting child maltreatment data is a complicated undertaking for many reasons (World Health Organization, 2016). Although governmental and other social data records are the gold standard for the data of many disciplines, social data records for child maltreatment have several significant issues. First, the definition of child maltreatment differs substantially depending on the geographic region, agency or organization, and purpose for data collection. Human memory is a function of various heuristic strategies so participant reports are influenced not only by characteristics of the event in question but also the experiences before, during, and after the event (Kahneman et al., 2000; Smallwood & O’Connor, 2011). In addition to these general issues with self-reported data, studies of child maltreatment may face additional limitations due to the sensitive nature of the questions. Individuals may intentionally withhold information related to child maltreatment due to social desirability, embarrassment, or concerns about confidentiality and the repercussions of reporting abuse (Everson et al., 2008). Concerns about repercussions may be especially prominent when talking to parents about their children’s experiences because many

institutional review boards and universities require researchers to report suspected child maltreatment to child protective services. Researchers may also directly ask minors about their experiences. This approach reduces the issues associated with retrospective report but is debated because children may not have the necessary perspective to recognize their experiences as abusive or to critically process the potential costs and benefits of disclosure (International Society for the Prevention of Child Abuse & Neglect, 2016). As cell phones have increased in popularity, more people are unreachable through a landline number. Also, cell phone service has not been equally adopted across the population so random digit dialing is likely to miss young people, people with low socio-economic status, and males (Lee et al., 2011). Stories about child maltreatment are making the headlines in newspapers because child abuse and neglect has become a recognized social problem whose consequences are being increasingly documented and discussed (Clément & Dufour, 2009; Franklin & Parton, 2001; Gilbert et al., 2009). Many people believe that publishing horror stories about children has contributed to the social recognition of maltreatment, the adoption of laws, and the creation of institutions with more efficient mechanisms for detecting and protecting mistreated children (American Humane Association, 2006; Franklin & Parton, 1991; Johnson, 1995; Watkins, 1990).

Literature Review Methods

We searched PsychInfo, PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Academic Search Elite using two search frameworks. The first framework was broadly focused on how social media and other forms of internet-based technology were used for health surveillance, which also included some broader epidemiologic research. The second framework focused on the use of social media for child maltreatment research. For each framework, one author reviewed the title and, if available, the abstract of all articles found through the search framework. Articles were considered possibly relevant if social media or internet-based approaches to health research or surveillance were discussed in the abstract. Articles with possibly relevant content were downloaded and the full text of the article was reviewed. For this review, social media was conceptualized using the Bright, Margetts, Hale, and Yasserli (2014) definition as “a means of communication, based around a website or internet service, where the content being communicated is produced by the people using the service.”

There has been little empirical research looking into the impact of the media on child protection. It is therefore necessary to consider studies conducted some time ago and others that have examined the impact of the media’s coverage of criminality. As Goddard and Saunders (2000) pointed out,

“Much of the literature that reviews the media and child abuse is critical rather than evaluative, and is based on approaches with little basis in theory” (p.121). When research into the coverage of child maltreatment in the print media is examined, two themes in particular stand out, that is the events that prompted the media to cover this theme and the nature of the content.

Child Abuse

Child abuse and neglect is any recent act or failure to act on the part of a parent or caretaker, which results in death, serious physical or emotional harm, sexual abuse or exploitation of a child. It is an act or failure to act which presents an imminent risk of serious harm to a child. (U.S. Child Abuse Prevention and Treatment Act) These types of abuse are more typically found in combination than alone. A physically abused child, for example, is often emotionally abused, and a sexually abused child also may be neglected.

Physical Abuse

Physical child abuse is the non-accidental infliction of physical injury to a child. They are characterized by injury, such as bruises, lesions and fractures that result from hitting (hand, stick, strap, or other object), punching, shaking, kicking, beating, choking, burning (with open flame or hot objects – boiling water, cigarettes), throwing, stabbing or otherwise harming a child. The parent or caretaker need not have intended to hurt the child for it to constitute physical abuse. Child abuse happens when a parent or other adult causes serious physical or emotional harm to a child. In the United States, the laws defining what constitutes child abuse vary from state to state, but generally speaking, child abuse can take these forms: physical abuse. Sexual abuse.

Physical abuse Indicators Include When the Child

- Reports injury by a parent or another adult caregiver.
- Has unexplained burns, bites, bruises, broken bones, black eyes, or welts in the shape of an object (wire hanger, stick, belt, etc).
- Has fading bruises or other noticeable marks.
- Seems frightened of the parents and protests or cries when it is time to go home.
- Flinches or cowers at the approach of adults. Consider the possibility of physical abuse when the parent or other adult caregiver:
- Offers conflicting, unconvincing, or no explanation for the child’s injury.
- Describes the child as ‘evil,’ or other negative way.
- Uses harsh physical discipline with the child.

Sexual Abuse

Any sexual behavior with - or sexual exploitation of - a child. There are three types of sexual offenses against children: Rape, molestation, distribution or production or possession of child pornography. Any vaginal or anal intercourse with a child is rape. A child cannot legally give consent to sexual activity. Sexual abuse is never a child’s fault.

Child sexual abuse includes a wide range of behaviors, including:

- Rape: vaginal or anal penile penetration.
- Oral sex by or to any adult.
- Genital contact with no intrusion.
- Fondling of a child’s breasts or buttocks.
- Indecent exposure.
- Production, distribution or possession of child pornography.
- Sexual Exploitation: Use of a child in prostitution, pornography.

Emotional Abuse

Emotional abuse is the ongoing emotional maltreatment of a child. It's sometimes called psychological abuse and can seriously damage a child's emotional health and development. Emotional abuse can involve deliberately trying to scare or humiliate a child or isolating or ignoring them.

Educational Abuse

Child maltreatment is common and takes many forms. From physical or emotional abuse, to child labor and other practices that violate their most basic rights. ... And at the same time, educational outcomes affect violence – education has been identified as a tool to reduce violence against children.

Neglect

Neglect is a pattern of failing to provide for a child's basic needs. It is abuse through omission; of not doing something resulting in significant harm or risk of significant harm.

There are four types of neglect: physical neglect, medical neglect, educational neglect and emotional neglect.

1. Physical neglect: Failure to provide food, weather appropriate clothing, supervision, a safe and clean home.
 2. Medical neglect: Failure to provide the necessary medical or dental care for a child's condition.
 3. Educational neglect: Failure to enroll a school-age child in school or to provide necessary special education. Allowing excessive absences from school.
 4. Emotional neglect: Failure to provide emotional support, love, and affection to a child
- Emotional.

The Content of Newspaper Articles on Maltreatment

It is worth noting that a very small proportion of all child abuse and neglect cases receive media attention. The stories reported on are often sensational and may involve tragic outcomes such as injuries or even death (for example, see Meunier, 2011). Indeed, when the media report on child maltreatment, it mainly covers events that are rare, unusual, or unpleasant (Aldridge, 1994; Franklin & Parton, 1991; Galilee, 2005; Laliberte, Larson, & Johnston, 2011; Saint-Jacques et al., 2010). The types of maltreatment that fall into these categories mainly include sexual and physical abuse. This sort of media coverage paints a distorted portrait of maltreatment, since child welfare agencies intervene most often in cases of negligence and exposure to domestic violence, which each represent 34% of maltreatment recorded in Canada (Public Health Agency of Canada, 2010 Studies by Saint-Jacques, M.-C., Villeneuve, P., Turcotte, D., Drapeau, S., Ivers, H. (2011). The role of media in reporting child abuse. *Journal of social service research*, 1-13.

Impact of the News Media on The number of Child Maltreatment Reports to CPS

At the time the present article was written, only one study (McDevitt, 1996) had empirically examined the impact of the media coverage of child maltreatment on the number of reports made to child protective services (CPS). Analyzing the titles of articles, this researcher counted up the number of articles per year dealing with abused children in two American newspapers, one national and one local, from 1963 to 1989. The counting of the number of abused children was conducted using national data brought together by the American Humane Association and the National Committee for the Prevention of Child Abuse. At the local level, the data were collected

by counting the number of new cases at the Allegheny County Children and Youth Services. The Saint-Jacques, M.-C., Villeneuve, P., Turcotte, D., Drapeau, S., Ivers, H. (2011). The role of media in reporting child abuse. *Journal of social service research*, results show that both the number of articles and the number of cases reported to welfare agencies steadily increased during this period.

Media Reports

Online media reports may also be used for public health surveillance. Individual researchers may monitor online reports or researchers may use databases that are automatically created or curated by other researchers. Examples of automated databases include HealthMap (Barboza et al., 2014; Brownstein et al., 2010; Chanlekha & Collier, 2010; Collier, 2010, 2012; Freifeld, Mandl, Reis, & Brownstein, 2008; Lyon, Nunn, Grosse, & Burgman, 2012); GENI-DB (Collier & Doan, 2012); Project Argus (Nelson, Li, Reilly, Hardin, & Hartley, 2012; Torii et al., 2011); ProMed-mail (Zhang, Dang, Chen, Thurmond, & Larson, 2009); MiTAP (Zhang et al., 2009); and Bio Caster (Lyon et al., 2012). In addition to existing databases, researchers may use text mining (Collier, 2011) or human analysts to identify media reports (Collier, 2011; Nerlich & Koteyko, 2012). Textmining of media reports may reduce the sources required for identification of articles but may not perform as well as human analysts (Collier, 2011). Human analysts have also been used to identify newspaper and website articles associated with drowning or near-drowning (Ferretti, De Angelis, Donati, & Torre, 2014; Zhu, Jiang, Li, Li, & Chen, 2015) and sudden cardiac death in athletes (Choi, Pan, Pock, & Chang, 2013).

Facebook

Facebook is an online social networking site where users create a profile, add other users to their network, send messages to their network connections, and post messages to their profiles. Users may also join common-interest groups and communicate with businesses. Similar to Twitter, Facebook may be used for active or passive data collection. It has frequently been used to recruit participants (Altshuler et al., 2015; Barratt et al., 2015; Bauermeister et al., 2012; Ben-Ezra et al., 2013; Hernandez-Romieu et al., 2014; Schumacher et al., 2014; Stein et al., 2014; Thomas et al., 2014; van Genderen et al., 2013), but the information created by users has also been used for research. Facebook users have the option of listing interests, such as movies, books, sports teams, activities, their profile. In one study, obesity prevalence in communities was predicted using Facebook interests (Chunara, Bouton, Ayers, & Brownstein, 2013). Geographical areas where a higher proportion of users endorsed activity-related interests, such as health and wellness or outdoor fitness activities, and a lower proportion of users endorsed interests in sedentary behaviors, particularly television watching, tended to have lower rates of obesity. Facebook “likes”, users’ expressions of interest or approval of posts, may also be used to predict health behaviors. The proportion of users by zip code who “like” certain categories of information is available through the advertising program interface. These data were significantly associated with life expectancy and many health conditions reported in the Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System (Gittelman et al., 2015).

Twitter

Twitter is a microblogging site where users post messages (tweets) that are 140 characters or less. Users may “follow” other users to see their posts on the front page. Users may also respond to tweets posted by other users, share (retweet) messages posted by other users, or approve (like) other posts. Users may use hashtags to categorize their messages. When a large number of users are posting with a hashtag, the hashtag is listed on the Twitter front page and is said to be

“trending.” There are multiple methods of researching with Twitter, including both active and passive data collection methods. As a passive data collection method, researchers may download existing information from Twitter. Alternatively, researchers may use Twitter as a platform for reaching participants. Regardless of the collection method, there are several ways Twitter data may be used for research and surveillance. The content of individual tweets may be examined to determine how people are discussing topics and changes in trending hashtags may be examined to determine how discussions around topics change over time. Social network analysis, examination of the relationships between users, may also be conducted to determine how information moves through networks. These analytic methods can be implemented by automated algorithms (Cao et al., 2015; Denecke et al., 2013; Odlum & Yoon, 2015; Paul & Dredze, 2014; Prieto, Matos, Alvarez, CACHEDA, & Oliveira, 2014; Yom-Tov, Borsa, Cox, & McKendry, 2014) or by human analysts. With life expectancy and many health conditions reported in the Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System (Gittelman et al., 2015). The content of Facebook groups may also be used to assess individual health behavior. Posts, comments, and photos in Facebook profiles and groups have been used to assess social support seeking among caregivers of children with autism spectrum disorder (MohdRoeei, Abdullah, & Basar, 2015), depressive symptoms (Moreno et al., 2011).

Limitations

This review had several limitations. First, the review excluded articles that were not published in English so important work conducted in other languages would not be included in this review. This limitation is common among reviews conducted by researchers from majority native-English-speaking countries; yet, future reviews may benefit from including other languages. Second, it was possible to define social media, internet-based technology, and surveillance in various ways. Differing definitions may have resulted in a different literature base to review. Finally, the search framework resulted in the inclusion of a variety of research designs, health outcomes, and technology approaches. This variety prevented quantitative comparisons across studies. However, as previously noted, that type of analysis is outside the scoping review framework, which focused on the extent, range, and nature of research concerning a focused topic, as well as the identification of gaps in the literature. As also noted, scoping reviews are ideal for topics with emerging evidence, such as social media.

Conclusions

Social media and internet-based technologies may be a promising approach to address the existing issues with child maltreatment data collection. However, it is necessary to account for the issues within each type of data collection approach and carefully validate the approach. Also, researchers should thoughtfully consider the ethical issues associated with both child maltreatment research and Internet-based research and take steps to protect participants before conducting future studies.

Web Sources

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